

Primality test amateur.

Dante Servi

This revision equals to a deletion.
Instead I want to point out two of my preprints on the same topic.

Primality test. My contribution.
Primality test. My second contribution.

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6380548>
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6397327>

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